

The Role of Emotional Intelligence in Adolescents in Socialization Processes

Alisherova Zulfia Tolibdjanovna

Doctoral student of Andijan State Institute of Redagogy

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Abstract: Emotional intelligence plays an important role in the socialization processes of adolescents, affecting their interactions with peers, family and society. This article examines the relationship between emotional intelligence and socialization during adolescence, determining how high levels of emotional intelligence contribute to improved social skills, stronger relationships, and healthy emotional development. By analyzing the literature, research on social behavior and emotional intelligence of adolescents is carried out, and the main elements affecting the results of socialization are clarified.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, adolescence, socialization, social skills, emotional development, interpersonal relationships.

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is an important developmental stage that drives important emotional, physical, and social changes. The process of socialization, learning to communicate with others and work within social norms is very important during this period. Emotional intelligence, the ability to recognize, understand, manage and influence emotions, is central to successful socialization. Adolescents with high emotional intelligence tend to form stronger social bonds, show empathy, and manage conflict more effectively.

In the mental development of a teenager, the content of the system of social interactions with others plays a key role. The need for communication with peers in adolescents. self-affirmation. The need for self-realization is strong.

One of the important characteristics of adolescence is the deepening of relationships with peers.

Adolescent than adults. strives to communicate closely with his peers. because they understand each other more, their worldviews and attitudes are closer to each other. Communication with adults could not replace communication with peers.

A teenager's attitude towards peers, friends, classmates is different from that of junior school age: his relationships are more multifaceted and meaningful.

In the period of adolescence, there are different relationships depending on the level of timeliness. Communication between them begins to go beyond educational activities and school and becomes a necessary and important area of a teenager's life. Communicating with peers puts education in second place, and communication with parents becomes uninteresting.

On the one hand in Osmir, striving for communication with peers, joint activities, on the other hand, the desire to be respected by his comrades is shown. This will be an important need.

Disappointment in relationships, not having the closest, or dystopia is the most serious problem for a teenager. Feeling alone is very difficult for a teenager.

Not being able to get along well with classmates, the teenager is now motivated to look for friends outside of school. A teenager finds them, but they are not always good.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

This article examines how emotional intelligence contributes to adolescent socialization and the implications for long-term emotional and social development.

Emotional intelligence plays a decisive role in the socialization processes of adolescents. During adolescence, socialization is a key stage of development where individuals learn to interact with peers, form relationships, and join social groups. How emotional intelligence affects this process:

Understanding and managing emotions, especially during adolescence, is key to developing Emotional Intelligence. Teens with high emotional intelligence are better equipped to handle the emotional ups and downs that come with this developmental stage. Here's a breakdown of those benefits:

Recognizing Emotions: Teenagers with high emotional intelligence are able to clearly identify their emotions. It helps them understand why they feel the way they do in different social situations, whether it's excitement, anger, or sadness. Being aware of these feelings can help you respond to them thoughtfully rather than impulsively.

Managing Negative Emotions: These individuals are better at dealing with negative emotions such as anger, frustration, or disappointment. Instead of letting these emotions lead to impulsive or disruptive behavior, emotionally intelligent teens are more likely to process their emotions in a calm and constructive way. This can lead to healthier outcomes in relationships, academics, and decision-making.

Managing Peer Relationships: High emotional intelligence also helps in managing complex emotions that arise from friendships and other social relationships. Adolescents with high emotional intelligence can understand the emotions of others, which helps them respond appropriately to conflicts, disagreements, or emotional exchanges. This can strengthen peer relationships and create a more supportive social environment.

These skills are important because they help teens build resilience, develop healthy relationships, and reduce stress during the turbulent teenage years. Emotional intelligence also plays an important role in long-term personal and professional success.

Empathy and social awareness:

Emotional intelligence enhances empathy, which is essential for:

- Understanding the feelings and perspectives of others leads to better communication and stronger social connections.
- Increasing social awareness, allowing adolescents to receive social signals and adapt their behavior in different social situations.
- Reducing misunderstandings or social friction, helping them build deeper and more meaningful relationships.

Conflict resolution

Teens with high emotional intelligence are generally better at:

- Resolve conflicts peacefully, taking into account the feelings and points of view of others.
- Effective communication of feelings without escalating tension, leading to more harmonious peer interactions.

Peer acceptance and social inclusion

Contributes to better social skills associated with emotional intelligence:

- Increased peer acceptance, as emotionally intelligent teens are more understanding and approachable.
- They are more likely to join social groups because they can better manage group dynamics.

Self-control and impulse control

Emotional intelligence helps teenagers:

- Managing impulsive behavior that can damage social relationships.
- Think before you react, it leads to more thoughtful and respectful relationships with peers.

Establish and maintain friendships

Teens with strong emotional intelligence:

- Build stronger, more stable friendships by being emotionally available and sensitive to their friends' needs.
- Maintain relationships by being flexible and resilient in the face of emotional issues such as disagreements or misunderstandings.

Dealing with peer pressure

Resistance to peer pressure emotional intelligence AIDS, as teenagers:

- They are better able to assert their values and beliefs without being distracted by the emotional manipulation of others.
- Can manage their emotions when faced with difficult social decisions, reducing the likelihood of engaging in risky behaviors.

Positive personality development

Emotional intelligence supports adolescents in developing a positive self-concept:

- Helping them process feelings of self-worth and identity that are often tested during social interactions.
- Encouraging self-reflection and emotional growth, helping the overall process of personality formation during adolescence.

Emotional intelligence is a key component of successful socialization during adolescence. It enhances empathy, self-control, communication, and conflict resolution, all of which are critical to building healthy relationships and solving the social challenges of this developmental stage.

The findings reinforce existing research that emotional intelligence is a critical factor in adolescent socialization. Adolescents with high emotional intelligence are better equipped to navigate social complexities, form meaningful relationships, and cope with emotional stress.

These adolescents tend to exhibit prosocial behaviors such as cooperation, empathy, and effective communication that are necessary for positive socialization.

Conversely, adolescents with low emotional intelligence often struggle with peer interactions, experience social rejection, or engage in negative behaviors such as aggression. This highlights the importance of developing emotional intelligence during adolescence, as it not only contributes to better social outcomes, but also supports overall psychological well-being.

Schools and community programs play an important role in supporting the development of emotional intelligence in adolescents. Emotional intelligence education, including skills such as emotional regulation, empathy, and stress management, should be incorporated into curricula to promote healthy socialization processes.

CONCLUSION

Research highlights the critical role of emotional intelligence in adolescent socialization. Adolescents with high emotional intelligence demonstrate better social skills, stronger relationships, and greater emotional resilience, which contribute to positive socialization experiences. These findings highlight the need for targeted interventions aimed at improving emotional intelligence in order to improve adolescent social functioning and emotional well-being.

Emotional intelligence programs: Schools and community organizations should implement programs that focus on developing emotional intelligence skills such as emotional regulation, empathy, and conflict resolution.

Parental Involvement: Parents should be encouraged to model and teach emotional intelligence at home through open communication and emotional support. **Counseling and support services:** Teens with low emotional intelligence should use counseling and peer support services to help them improve their emotional skills and social relationships.

More research: More research is needed to examine the long-term effects of emotional intelligence development on social and emotional outcomes in older adults.

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